

Using IPCC scenarios to challenge new oil and gas infrastructure: Analysis in *Science* is fragile

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Introduction

In 2024, the journal *Science* published a Policy Forum by Fergus Green *et al.*, titled “No new fossil fuel projects: The norm we need.”¹

In the article, Green *et al.* analyze selected low-carbon scenarios from the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) to “show that no new fossil fuel projects are needed in a 1.5°C world: Existing fossil fuel capital stock is sufficient to meet energy demand in representative scenarios aligned with the Paris Agreement target of limiting global warming to 1.5°C.”

The use of IPCC scenarios to inform policy around climate change and fossil fuels is well-established and important, as are the potential climate benefits of limiting new fossil fuel infrastructure. And, while Green *et al.* make useful observations about political norms, their quantitative scenario analysis is flawed.

Here, I present evidence of three distinct problems with their analysis of IPCC (and other) scenarios. The first two problems concern technical aspects of data and analysis for which there should be clear, straightforward solutions. Those two are:

1. **A unit conversion error**, in which data in the published figure (as well as Figure S1 and Data S1 in the Supplementary Materials) is taken from a private source but not accurately converted;
2. **An unsupported conclusion** that appears to be contradicted by their own data, when the authors claim that “in short, existing fossil fuel infrastructure is sufficient to meet energy demand in the **vast majority** of scenarios consistent with the 1.5°C objective” (bold emphasis added).

The final, third problem raises more foundational concerns about the authors’ evidence, and for which I expect there could be room for reasonable disagreement:

¹ Green *et al.* 2024. *Science*; 384 (6699): 954-957. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adn6533>.

3. **A methodological bias**, in which the authors use a scenario selection method that is inappropriate for making broad claims about what constitutes “representative” 1.5°C scenarios.

In this document, I discuss the three problems in Green *et al.* 2024 in detail,² while attempting to replicate selected findings. While I show the authors’ results to be fragile, I do see ways to make them stronger. Accordingly, at the end of discussing each problem, I also suggest possible corrections that could lead to a more robust scientific record.

Problem #1: The authors use inaccurate data to assess oil production from existing fields.

In panel 2 of their figure (reproduced and annotated below), Green *et al.* present historical and forecast gas and oil extraction adapted from Rystad Energy’s UCube, a commercially available industry database. However, the historical data appear incorrect. For example, the reported 2022 historical value of 220 EJ from “producing fields” is higher than 2022 production reported by the IEA of 188 EJ.³ The discrepancy is plainly visible in the authors’ figure (reproduced and annotated below): as historical (2020-2022) oil production from “Producing fields” (light-grey shading in panel 2) is noticeably higher than reported by the IEA (line labeled IEA NZE 2023).⁴

² Each problem existed upon publication of the article in 2024, has not been addressed by other subsequent corrections, and can have a solution that does not depend on any information published since the end of 2023. Note that Green *et al.* also published an eLetter on the *Science* website dated February 6, 2026, responding to questions posed in my own eLetter of December 15, 2025. All references to Green *et al.* in this document are to the 2024 article unless specifically described as referring to their eLetter.

³ IEA [World Energy Balances Highlights](#). Accessed February 3, 2026.

⁴ The discrepancy is also visible in figure S1 and data S1, where historical oil production in Green *et al.*’s Rystad data is substantially higher than IEA (as already stated), DNV, BNEF, Navigant, and every other source listed.

Figure 1. Forecasted global extraction, adapted from Green et al. 2024 with 2022 actual oil production (from IEA World Energy Balances) and adjusted decline of existing fields (thick red line in right-hand panel)

Small discrepancies are not necessarily a problem, as different data sources can use slightly different definitions of “oil” or the energy contained therein. But here, the discrepancy is large, and it appears to be caused by a simple unit-conversion error.

Green et al.’s Table S3 shows their database query script, which directs UCube to convert liquids production from the base, volumetric unit of barrels (bbl) into an energy-based unit for every oil or gas field globally, aggregating to a global total for years 2020 through 2050. The authors then use these global totals in their main figure (as shown above), figure S1, and data S1.

Green et al. do not report the energy content (i.e., energy contained in a volumetric barrel of liquids) used by their script to do the conversion and Rystad does not appear to publish it. However, based on communication with Rystad staff, UCube (and therefore Green et al.) uses a simplified, default energy content of 1 barrel = 1 barrel oil equivalent = 6.12 EJ for all liquids.⁵

⁵ This was confirmed by email communication with Debbie Lee, Rystad Energy Support Team, February 8, 2026 (full email exchange between Peter Erickson and Rystad staff available upon request), and which exactly matches that in BP Statistical Review of World Energy: [Approximate Conversion Factors](#).

Using a single default energy content, however, introduces a serious error into use of Rystad data for Green *et al.*'s purpose,⁶ which is to compare Rystad's data to other global scenarios for purposes of showing that new oil and gas fields are not needed.⁷ This is because using a single default energy content for *all* liquids – including the substantial portion of the liquids (such as natural gas liquids) that typically have an energy content of 4 GJ/barrel or less⁸ – leads to Green *et al.*'s estimates of global oil production from existing fields being erroneously high.

The consequence of the discrepancy is that Green *et al.* are overestimating, by about 15%, how much oil would come from existing fields (the grey shading in the figures), which is one of the most important parts of their logic. Any oil in their analysis that doesn't come from *existing* fields must come from *new* fields, and so the authors could well be —as a further consequence – underplaying the potential need for new oil fields in the IPCC (and other) scenarios they examine.

More robust approaches are clearly available. Green *et al.* could either perform their own, bottom-up conversions of volumetric barrels to exajoules (EJ) for each type of liquid; or else cross-check, and then adjust, their starting oil production values from UCube to match widely-accepted global oil production values in EJ (e.g. from IEA) in energy terms; or both. In fact, Green *et al.*'s data source – Rystad Energy – recognizing the discrepancy, *themselves do such a conversion* when they show their oil production values on the same chart as IEA, OPEC, and others (see Attachment 1).

In an eLetter dated February 6, 2026 on the *Science* website, Green *et al.* set aside my concern about the discrepancy between Rystad and IEA historical oil, arguing that there is no single “actual” value for oil production,⁹ since “modellers and data providers convert volumes to energy by different methods”. That is, of course, true, but it does not justify using a method known to be in error.¹⁰

⁶ Rystad itself may not view its use of a single default energy content as an error, as they are making a simplifying assumption that may not interfere with the primary uses of the UCube database, which is to help customers plan activities supporting some 80,000 oil and gas fields globally. Nevertheless, such an assumption is not fit for the purpose that Green *et al.* apply it to.

⁷ “Need” is, of course, a slippery concept. In the context of global energy, “need” would seem to involve a whole host of factors; in that context, whether something is “needed” cannot be determined by simply comparing lines in a model's output. But as Green *et al.* use the term in their article, so too will I.

⁸ NGLs comprised about 20% of world oil production in 2022 per IEA, and have an energy content of 4 GJ/barrel or less per BP Statistical Review of World Energy: [Approximate Conversion Factors](#).

⁹ Using IEA for actual historical data is common. See, e.g. Figure 9: World Oil Demand in Zhu *et al.* 2025: [Global Energy Outlook 2025: Headwinds and Tailwinds in the Energy Transition](#).

¹⁰ Green *et al.* note in their eLetter that energy content differences may be “interesting”, and perform their own conversion in the Supplementary Materials, claiming that doing so does not affect their overall

Green *et al.* should correct their historical and forecast oil extraction, anchoring and adjusting that data series to the best estimate of oil production (in EJ) in the last year (2022) of their historical data. I suggest that anchoring value should be 188 EJ in 2022, as reported in the IEA's World Energy Balances, and which would result in Green *et al.*'s oil extraction data series being reduced by about 15% in all years, as shown by the thick red line in the figure above.

Problem #2: The authors claim that “existing fossil fuel infrastructure is sufficient to meet energy demand in the vast majority of scenarios consistent with the 1.5°C objective”, but their own data do not support this.

On page 955 (third column), the authors claim: “In short, existing fossil fuel infrastructure is sufficient to meet energy demand in the **vast majority** of scenarios consistent with the 1.5°C objective” (bold emphasis added; a similar claim is made in the second column of page 955). However, the authors do not define or justify “vast majority”, and they do not indicate which scenarios meet their claim of sufficient fossil fuel infrastructure and which do not, making it difficult to verify.

In fact, the left panel of their figure plainly shows that even their own analysis may not support their finding: as shown in the zoomed-in panel below, gas production from existing fields (those already-producing plus under-development) in 2040 is less than gas demand from Green *et al.*'s median selected IPCC 1.5°C pathway. The median is, by definition, the point where half the scenarios show *even greater* gas demand. This means that, by Green *et al.*'s own chart, at least half of their selected 26 scenarios demand more gas than provided by existing fields by the late 2030s.

conclusions. Still, it does not justify publishing data known to be in error. It is also not assured that, once this *and other problems* (as discussed in the next sections) are addressed, that their conclusions would hold.

Green *et al.* may believe the amount of new gas needed by 2040 – a median of 10 EJ per data S1 – is small, and could perhaps be partially compensated by surplus from earlier years. But that would not provide much validation for the authors’ conclusions, as the 2040 cutoff of their analysis is arbitrary, and the discrepancy between gas demand and supply increases steadily to a median of about 42 EJ by 2050, as shown in the authors’ data S1.¹¹

Turning now to oil, already-existing oil fields are, like gas fields, unable to meet demand in a non-trivial fraction of Green *et al.*’s selected 26 IPCC 1.5°C scenarios. This can also be seen in data S1, where oil production from existing fields in 2035 is less than the 25th percentile of oil demand across scenarios.

Looking now at oil and gas *together*, about 20 of 26 of the authors’ selected scenarios (77%) would fall short in supply of either oil or gas without new fields by around 2040. This analysis, while approximate, casts substantial doubt on Green *et al.*’s claim of new oil and gas fields being unneeded in the “**vast majority** of scenarios consistent with the 1.5°C objective” (again, bold emphasis added).¹²

¹¹ Note that the authors limit their analysis to 2040 (and not beyond) in order to give a “more plausible and robust picture” (Supplementary Materials, page 5). Perhaps it is true that uncertainty increases with longer time horizons, but limiting the analysis to the near-term does not *inherently* mean that the resulting analysis is more plausible or robust. Furthermore, it may not be the case that gas rebound after 2040 in the IPCC scenarios can be dismissed as an “artefact” (meaning, as I understand it, a feature of the model that does not actually reflect a real physical or economic phenomenon) as the authors state (SM, p. 5). Gas rebound could be due to power system dynamics (e.g. increasing deployment of gas-fired power plants with CCS to meet specific needs), the growth of gas use in industry, or other legitimate modeling outcomes that cannot be so easily dismissed as being “unlikely”.

¹² Green *et al.* briefly discuss an “alternative analytical approach” that “would compare fossil fuel reserves or cumulative lifetime production with carbon budgets” (p. 955, third column), and which they claim would also

Lastly, turning to unabated gas power generation, 6 of 26 of the author’s selected scenarios demand more generation capacity globally than would be provided by existing units by 2040. But unlike for gas and oil, which can be traded globally (involving long distances between producers from consumers), cross- or inter-continent electricity transmission is much less common. Accordingly, it is less appropriate to use *global* supply and demand imbalances for electricity than it is for other fuels.

Green *et al.* mention this tension when they note “minor discrepancies in gas power capacity and modeled demand in India and Sub-Saharan Africa” (p. 955, third column), but they do not (unlike for global totals) report the regional scenario data. Nevertheless, Green *et al.*’s scenarios display an increase in median unabated gas power capacity in southern Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa of about 50% between 2025 and 2040 (suggesting construction of the equivalent of 230 new, 400 MW unabated gas-fired power plants in southern Asia, and 60 new, 300 MW facilities in Sub-Saharan Africa)¹³. Furthermore, nearly all (19 of 20) of Green *et al.*’s scenarios show new, unabated gas power in one or both of these major world regions (the total scenario count here is 20, not 26, because not all IPCC models show regional results).

These findings for gas power are not “minor discrepancies”¹⁴; these results – from regions representing about a third of global population – cast yet additional doubt on Green *et al.*’s claims that existing fossil fuel infrastructure can meet demand “in the vast majority of scenarios consistent with the 1.5°C objective”.

In their 2026 eLetter, Green *et al.* decline to address my question about how many scenarios support their findings. Instead of counting individual scenarios, Green *et al.* argue that it is “more appropriate to use a suite of scenarios—representing a range of

arrive at the conclusion that new fossil fuel supply (including new oil and gas fields) would “generate enough carbon dioxide emissions to exhaust the remaining 1.5C carbon budget”. That may be true (given how small the remaining 1.5C carbon budget is, one could point to a wide variety of actions that could tip the world over the 1.5C budget), but a gesture to an alternate method hardly justifies Green *et al.*’s errors here.

¹³ Power plant equivalencies here are estimated by dividing the total median capacity needs in GW for each region (18 GW in Sub-Saharan Africa; 95 GW in southern India: see Attachment 2) by the average size per unit in development in each region as imputed from Global Energy Monitor’s Global Oil and Gas Plant Tracker (January 2026 release).

¹⁴ Green *et al.* include another qualifier in their “no new fossil” norm; that it applies to “large scale” power plants, though that remains undefined, and the authors do not identify large- versus small-scale infrastructure in their analysis in their figure or data S1. The amount of capacity added in southern Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa is clearly not small, but even in other regions, new unabated gas power plants could still be implied by the scenario models, e.g. to replace old equipment and serve as “peakers” with low capacity factors. See, e.g. Bistline, J.E.T., Young, D.T. The role of natural gas in reaching net-zero emissions in the electric sector. *Nat Commun* 13, 4743 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-32468-w>. If these peakers are the types of plants that Green *et al.* meant to exclude by referring to “large scale” power plants, the authors should say so.

possible futures—to guide policy decisions.” Continuing, their “aim in using these scenarios was to determine whether our proposed norm against new fossil fuel projects would help to achieve the 1.5°C goal without significant threat of failing to meet energy demand. We found that in the median and interquartile range of the assessed scenarios, demand for oil and gas is less than or approximately matches supply from existing fields, implying that adopting our proposed norm need not create significant disruptions to 1.5°C-aligned energy demand.”

This response is perplexing, in part because it makes Green *et al.*'s method of judging scenarios *less* transparent and replicable than in the original article. In the 2024 article, the method is described as a comparison, over time, of energy supply from already-existing infrastructure to the energy demanded in 1.5°C scenarios, suggesting that simple arithmetic could be used to perform the comparison for each year. Now, the words *significant* and *approximately* are introduced as qualifiers but are not defined, hindering attempts at replication.

Furthermore, basing their analytical method on medians and inter-quartile ranges (IQRs) of a “suite of scenarios” is not a reasonable proxy for looking at the individual scenarios that make up that suite, especially when multiple variables are involved (oil, gas, coal power, and gas power). Using just medians and IQRs makes it impossible to see whether scenarios that don't need new fossil fuel infrastructure in one year in one variable may demand such in another year or another variable.¹⁵

Nevertheless, in Attachment 2, I attempt to replicate Green *et al.*'s findings concerning there being “no need” for new fossil fuel infrastructure, here defining (given lack of better information) a “significant disruption” as one for which demand does not exceed supply from existing infrastructure by more than 20% in 2030, 2035, or 2040.¹⁶

¹⁵ Further, to readers unfamiliar with the use of scenario medians, the median may read as if it itself were a representative scenario (it is, of course, not: the median is a descriptive statistic, calculated in each year for each variable, and it can fall between different scenarios in each time period and variable).

¹⁶ This definition of “significant” is arbitrary but is intended to reflect the approximate nature of Green *et al.*'s comparisons given the limited information they provided. Using a 20% buffer also implicitly allows market participants some flexibility to shift oil or gas supply over time to accommodate expected future shortfalls. That flexibility may be important to the authors since, in their eLetter, they also introduce a new, illustrative metric that would compare *cumulative* demand between 2020 and 2040 to supply from existing fields. I do not adopt that full new, cumulative metric here, because that approach would suffer from three problems: (1) it implies the oil and gas industry could shut in production from annual global surpluses of up to 40% of production in the mid/late 2020s and then re-start in the 2030s, even as the economic incentive for doing so would be diminished; (2) denying new fields on this cumulative logic could lead to a huge and disruptive supply cliff at (or shortly after) Green *et al.*'s arbitrary cutoff end-date of 2040, as existing fields are exhausted but no new fields come online; (3) industry investors do not generally plan for cumulative supply over fixed,

In so doing, I find that six scenarios for oil, nine scenarios for gas, five scenarios for *global* gas power, and 13 scenarios across these three variables display demand levels such that, without new fossil fuel infrastructure, “significant disruptions” would occur. These 13 scenarios, representing half of Green *et al.*’s set of 26, demonstrate that, even by Green *et al.*’s own method and logic, it is not correct to say that the “existing fossil fuel infrastructure is sufficient to meet energy demand in the vast majority of scenarios consistent with the 1.5°C objective.” Importantly, significant disruptions in unabated gas power generation would occur in sub-Saharan Africa or south Asia in additional seven scenarios, for a total of 20 scenarios, firmly disproving Green *et al.*’s claim that a “majority” of their 26 scenarios would not need new fossil fuel infrastructure to meet demand.

Furthermore, regardless of the validity of Green *et al.*’s scenario findings, it seems authors of a scientific article claiming to assess the “vast majority” of some quantifiable number of things would be able to say how many and which things make up the vast majority (and which do not).¹⁷ By contrast, for the authors to deny providing such a tally seems contrary to *Science*’s commitment to data and analytical transparency.

Thankfully, clear solutions exist for the problem of Green *et al.*’s unsupported “vast majority” conclusion. Namely, the authors should remove the claim of “vast majority”; clearly state their arithmetic without qualifiers such as “approximately”; and accurately describe what their scenarios show, including disclosing which of their 26 scenarios support their conclusions (and for what types of fossil fuel infrastructure and in what years and world regions).

These suggested corrections to Green *et al.* are clear and straight-forward, and they should be uncontroversial. Once made, and based on my analysis here, I expect that the corrections could, in turn, lead to modest but important changes in the authors’ conclusions. For example:

- **Green *et al.*’s conclusion for oil and gas fields can likely be preserved, with changes.** Specifically, the conclusion that “demand for oil and gas in the scenarios could be met from fields already in production or under development” would need to be qualified to hold only in certain scenarios and only if feasibility concerns in

two-decade windows; they instead look mainly at price expectations, which tend to converge to the marginal cost of developing new fields.

¹⁷ To this, Green *et al.* may argue, as on page 5 of the Supplementary Materials, that scenarios “should be taken illustratively rather than statistically; scenario sets should not be treated as a statistical sample”. These are fair points, but if the authors themselves use descriptive statistics such as majority, median, and interquartile range, *Science*’s [editorial policies](#) would seem to demand that these calculations (including claims of “majority”) be verifiable: “Authors should describe statistical methods with enough detail to enable a knowledgeable reader with access to the original data to verify the results”.

those scenarios can be overcome. (I will discuss these feasibility considerations under Problem #3 below). The conclusion for gas specifically would need to be qualified to only hold through about 2035 (not through 2040, as currently implied).

- **The conclusion about unabated gas power plants would need to be dropped or substantially scaled back.** Specifically, the claim that “existing and under-construction gas power infrastructure is sufficient to meet projected demand under most scenarios” is not supported by the evidence. Still, this conclusion (and supporting evidence) could be retained in limited form if constrained to certain regions and appropriately qualified (e.g. what types of gas power plants are still constructed in the scenarios).

Finally, while these changes to Green *et al.*'s conclusions follow directly from correcting the data and analysis errors identified in problems #1 and #2, Problem #3, which follows, discusses a more foundational concern.

Problem 3: The authors discarded 71 of 97 IPCC 1.5°C as not feasible, but that doesn't make their selected 26 scenarios any more feasible, realistic, or credible.

Under Problem 2, above, I showed that Green *et al.*'s claim about the “majority” of their selected 26 1.5°C scenarios not needing new fossil fuel infrastructure is incorrect. Here I expand that observation to show that, because the authors discarded 71 of 97 1.5°C - consistent scenarios, they cannot make any broad claims about “representative” 1.5°C scenarios (page 954, column 3; and page 955, column 2).¹⁸

Namely, Green *et al.* use highly selective logic to exclude 71 of the IPCC's C1 scenarios. As explained in their Supplemental Materials, the authors use three feasibility criteria (related to carbon sequestration) out of the IPCC's much larger set of 18. The authors justify their three criteria in large part because “fossil fuels and especially natural gas production and consumption pathways are highly sensitive to assumptions about levels of carbon sequestration” (Supplementary Materials, page 4). As evidence for this sensitivity, they cite Achakulwisut, *et al.* 2023 which, indeed, finds that imposing a (somewhat different) set of carbon sequestration limits “implies much faster and greater reductions in fossil fuel

¹⁸ More specifically, from page 954, column 3: “Existing fossil fuel capital stock is sufficient to meet energy demand in representative scenarios aligned with the Paris Agreement target of limiting global warming to 1.5°C.” Green *et al.* do not specify what they mean by “representative” or explain why they believe their scenarios to be representative, but a plain-language interpretation would suggest that whatever scenarios are selected share the relevant important characteristics (here, characteristics related to fossil fuel infrastructure) with the entire population (e.g. of the full set of 97 scenarios). As I show, there is little reason to think that Green *et al.*'s selected scenarios are representative when it comes to oil and gas.

supply and use compared to the full AR6 ensemble, especially for gas, in the near- and long-term.”

But Green *et al.*'s justification raises an important methodological question, as it creates a potential circularity in the logic. If the authors knew that limiting carbon sequestration potential would limit natural gas (and potentially other fossil fuel) production, then it gives the appearance that the authors are assuming one of the things they set out to prove – that gas demand in the scenarios is low enough that it “could be met from fields already in production or under development”.¹⁹

Even if that logical structure could be justified, however, there are still problems. The first, and easiest to address, is that the authors do not specify what IPCC database variables they use to correspond to their three chosen scenario-selection criteria, an oversight that hinders replication.²⁰

The second and more important problem is that by using a scenario filtering process intended to limit concerns about risk and feasibility (and its close cousin, “uncertainty about deliverability”), the authors are implicitly making an argument about the feasibility of one subset of scenarios relative to another. The problem is, they provide no *explicit* argument of this and no actual data that would allow the reader to gauge whether and how the selected 26 scenarios are more or less feasible than the discarded scenarios.²¹

Put another way, their analysis depends on 1.5°C being feasible, by their selected 26 C1 scenarios. Otherwise, oil and gas demand would not be able to decline as fast as in their figure, and even more new oil and gas fields may be needed to avoid significant disruption.

¹⁹ Indeed, median gas production in Green *et al.*'s 26 selected scenarios is 95 EJ in 2030 and 78 EJ in 2040, which is 23% lower in 2030 and 7% lower in 2040 than the median of all discarded scenarios. Median oil production in the 26 selected scenarios is lower than in the discarded scenarios by an even greater amount.

²⁰ The most obvious variable in the IPCC AR6 scenario database to use for fossil CCS (Green *et al.*'s threshold: 3.8 Gt CO₂/year) would be Carbon Sequestration|CCS|Fossil. The most obvious variable for BECCS (3 Gt CO₂/year) would be Carbon Sequestration|CCS|Biomass. The most obvious variable for afforestation and reforestation (3.6 Gt CO₂/year) would be either Carbon Sequestration|Land Use|Afforestation or the more general Carbon Sequestration|Land Use, but I could not replicate the authors' results using either of these variables. I believe the authors instead used Emissions|CO₂|AFOLU, which is more widely reported across models. If so, the authors should justify their application of the 3.6 GtCO₂/year threshold (intended as being on afforestation and reforestation) to *this sector-wide AFOLU* variable that also includes additional land-based sequestration practices such as improved agricultural soil carbon and biochar, the inclusion of which would seem to increase the maximum feasible potential beyond 3.6 GtCO₂/year (Fuss *et al.* 2018).

²¹ The only mention of broader feasibility or credibility comes in the Supplemental Materials: “...there are no 1.5°C scenarios that meet all of these [18] criteria simultaneously”, an observation that suggests perhaps 1.5°C is no longer feasible without high overshoot, which, if true, would seem to render Green *et al.*'s analysis moot, as its logic depends on 1.5°C being feasible by the no or low-overshoot C1 scenarios. Green *et al.* may believe that they needed to make choices to allow for some scenarios to be analyzed, but if these scenarios are not feasible by their own threshold, then their logic is contradictory.

And yet, all of Green *et al.*'s selected scenarios would face their own serious feasibility concerns. In fact, each of the authors 26 selected scenarios exceeds their own feasibility threshold – “medium” level of concern²² – at some point between 2030 and 2050 in at least 6 of 15 other criteria besides carbon sequestration²³.

These concerns compound such that, overall, Green *et al.*'s selected 26 scenarios could face *greater, more* disruptive overall feasibility challenges in the near-term (through 2030) than the 71 scenarios they set aside (see Attachment 3).

The point here is not that the IPCC's feasibility assessment will necessarily end up being definitive (indeed, the IPCC's assessment in Chapter 3 of AR6 Working Group III was preliminary, and substantial work on this topic is ongoing), but instead that Green *et al.*'s focus on carbon sequestration feasibility is narrow, and their results likely contingent on that narrow view. Had one instead taken a different view of what feasibility concerns to highlight, one could have found markedly different findings about new oil or gas fields.

Imagine, for example, a different set of researchers concerned about the feasibility of rapidly scaling up wind power, which has been growing more slowly than solar power. That group of researchers could look at the same IPCC source as Green *et al.* and select just the 17 IPCC C1 scenarios that displayed *low* concern for the needed pace of scaling wind power.²⁴ Remarkably, this set would have zero overlap with the 26 scenarios selected by Green *et al.*, all of which (if so-rated by the IPCC) received a *medium* or *high* rating for concern about the pace of scaling wind power.²⁵ And, these other 17 scenarios show median demand for oil in 2040 that is more than twice as much as in Green *et al.*'s scenarios. The point here is not that scaling wind power is any less feasible than scaling carbon sequestration (or that more oil will *necessarily* end up being needed); it's that alternate, reasonable (if particular) concerns over feasibility can lead to very different findings. Because of this, Green *et al.*'s findings should be considered fragile.

²² The authors exclude scenarios that meet the IPCC's threshold for “medium” level of concern for carbon sequestration (Supplementary Information, page 4).

²³ Green *et al.* substitute Fuss *et al.* (2018)'s analysis of afforestation and reforestation potential, stating (in their Supplemental Materials) that the IPCC AR6 “did not assess” these dimensions. In fact, the IPCC's assessment of “forest cover increase” was intended to assess afforestation (per the underlying source Brutschin *et al.* 2021: doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abf0ce). Nevertheless, for simplicity, the 15 “other” criteria I consider are the 18 in Table 8 of IPCC, 2022. Annex III, minus “BECCS scale-up”, “Fossil CCS scale-up”, and “Forest cover increase”).

²⁴ A low rating for concern means the scenario requires less than a 10-percentage-point increase per decade in global share of electricity generation from wind.

²⁵ Eleven of Green *et al.*'s 26 scenarios received a *high* rating for concerns about wind feasibility; 12 received a *medium* rating; 3 were not rated. For a list of the 17 scenarios that received a *low* concern rating for the pace of scaling wind power, and comparison to Green *et al.*'s set, see the last page of Attachment 3.

To give a further sense of how Green *et al.*'s conclusions may not be representative, below I show all IPCC C1 scenarios that report oil and gas demand, as adapted from Figure 1 of Achakulwisut *et al.* (2023).²⁶ This figure displays the IPCC C1 scenarios in **blue**,²⁷ with production from existing oil and gas fields super-imposed in **red** (for oil, I use the “existing fields *after adjustment*” line from panel 2 of the figure above.).

Figure 2. Global primary energy production in the IPCC’s C1(1.5°C) scenarios (light blue lines; median is dark blue line) compared to adjusted oil and gas decline pathways from Green *et al.* 2024. Adapted from Figure 1 panels (d) and (g) in Achakulwisut, Erickson, *et al.* 2023.

When looking at this larger population of scenarios, a greater share of C1 scenarios leave room for new oil or gas fields than in Green *et al.*'s subset. Namely, about 66% of all C1 scenarios show oil demand exceeding what is available from existing fields by 2040, compared to 35% in Green *et al.*'s subset. For gas, about 76% of all C1 scenarios show gas demand exceeding what is available from existing fields by 2040, compared to 65% in Green *et al.*'s subset. In other words, the authors' 26 scenarios do not appear representative of the full population when it comes to oil and gas. (Green *et al.*'s subset also relies disproportionately on only 3 out of 10 models generating C1 scenarios – 15 scenarios from MESSAGE, 6 from REMIND, and 5 from WITCH.²⁸)

²⁶ Achakulwisut, Ploy, Peter Erickson, *et al.* Global fossil fuel reduction pathways under different climate mitigation strategies and ambitions. *Nat Commun* 14, 5425 (2023),

²⁷ Or, more precisely, all such scenarios that show primary energy demand for oil and gas (n=94).

²⁸ The high reliance on MESSAGE is notable because that model does not consider potential carbon sequestration from direct air capture (DAC) or enhanced weathering technologies, even as these approaches may prove important in later decades and are included in several other models (including WITCH, which includes DAC, and for which Green *et al.*'s scenarios show about 80% more oil consumption in 2040 as for their selected MESSAGE scenarios). More broadly, the potential for DAC may be under-represented in the AR6 models. (See Supplementary Note #6 in Edwards *et al.* 2024: doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2215679121).

Of course, the authors are free to analyze any subset of the 97 IPCC 1.5°C -consistent scenarios that they wish, and filtering for different subsets of scenarios is a common way to illustrate the trade-offs inherent in different choices.²⁹ Still, as the IPCC says in the same part of *Annex III* from which Green *et al.* take their feasibility thresholds, "...scenarios need to be looked at as a set to understand attainable outcomes and the trade-offs between them. With scenarios, context matters."³⁰ The problem here is that Green *et al.* provide no information about trade-offs (such as their scenario subset's faster and more disruptive retirement of existing coal plants; higher carbon prices; and greater reliance on vegetarian diets, with associated decline in pasture land³¹), and precious little about the larger context of the full set of 97 scenarios. Instead, Green *et al.* seem to be making definitive claims about what is not needed in "representative" (or "credible", as asserted on page 955, second column) 1.5°C scenarios, in ways that do not appear supportable.³²

Here, I can imagine some readers arguing that my critique of how Green *et al.* selected their scenarios is too pedantic, and that given the regulatory and political context of fossil fuel infrastructure, the precise details of scenario-selection are less important than, say clear, actionable, directional policy analysis. (Furthermore, Green *et al.*'s scenarios could be more *desirable* in other ways not reflected by feasibility concerns.) Perhaps Green *et al.* would share these views, and I am sympathetic to these considerations. Still, the authors do provide clear, actionable policy analysis in their "Political economy of new versus existing projects" (beginning on page 955) section, which advances well-reasoned (if narrow) arguments about new fossil fuel projects being (for example) morally "inappropriate". But note: as Green *et al.* describe clearly upfront (page 954, third column), that political economy analysis is a distinct (and subsequent) analytical step from their first step of scenario analysis. Each step – including the scenario analysis – must stand on its own for their overall argument to succeed. (Had Green *et al.* wanted to invoke moral, legal, or other desirability considerations beyond feasibility in their scenario selection process, they could have done so, while clearly stating such and still providing justification, context and trade-offs with respect to the full scenario set.)

²⁹ For a foundational description of the purpose and appropriate uses of IPCC scenarios, see, e.g. Nakicenovic, N. & Swart, R. IPCC special report on emissions scenarios: a special report of working group III of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. (2000). See also: Box 1 in Huppman *et al* 2018: doi.org/10.1038/s41558-018-0317-4.

³⁰ Source: page 1870 of IPCC, 2022: Annex III: Scenarios and modelling methods [Guivarch, C., E. *et al.*, (eds)]. In IPCC, 2022: Climate Change 2022: Mitigation of Climate Change. Contribution of Working Group III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.

³¹ See Attachment 3 for further discussion of these feasibility criteria and their associated dimensions.

³² Even as "representativeness or comprehensiveness are indeed critical to produce a well-founded and authoritative analysis". Source: Guivarch *et al.* 2022 "Using large ensembles of climate change mitigation scenarios for robust insights" *Nature Climate Change*. (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-022-01349-xm>)

In their 2026 eLetter responding to my initial questions, Green *et al.* state that their scenario filtering approach is consistent with those “widely used in the literature”, for which they cite the 2019 Production Gap Report as the example. That analysis, however, used a threshold for BECCS of 5 Gt CO₂ in mid-century (not 3 Gt CO₂ as in Green *et al.*); it also used a different scenario database (that associated with the IPCC’s *Special Report on Global Warming of 1.5°C*). When the Production Gap Report (PGR) updated the analysis in 2023 to use (like Green *et al.*) the IPCC AR6 database, the BECCS threshold of 5 Gt CO₂ /yr was maintained, leading to 10 additional scenarios being included relative (on net) to Green *et al.*’s set, for a total of 36.³³ The PGR results for oil differed markedly than for Green *et al.*, with a median 50% higher in 2040 than in Green *et al.*’s set,³⁴ indicating a greater potential for new oil fields. Thus, Green *et al.*’s scenario filtering approach does not appear consistent with the source they cite as justification.

Green *et al.* also defend their use of filters on carbon capture and storage (CCS) and carbon dioxide removal (CDR) in their eLetter, arguing that – due to slow progress on these technologies – “scenarios with very ambitious CDR or CCS do not reflect the world we are in. For informing policy-making, reflection of real-world trends is more important than in scholarly explorations of possible futures” (eLetter, paragraph 6). I agree that using filters on CCS or CDR potentials is not wrong, *per se*. However, if Green *et al.* are serious about policymaking for “the world we are in” based on “real-world trends”, they should also contend with other dimensions of feasibility, namely the 15 *other* real-world feasibility criteria examined by the IPCC source but discarded by the authors. As I have shown here, those criteria indicate that Green *et al.*’s selected scenarios may display *even worse, more disruptive* feasibility concerns. Policymaking can act on *any* of these dimensions – be they fossil fuel supply (as in Green *et al.*), fossil fuel demand, CDR deployment, the pace of renewable power build-out, or the underlying feasibility factors.

Finally, in their eLetter, Green *et al.* describe how the world has evolved in the two years since their Policy Forum, with additional fossil fuel infrastructure constructed, such that “even faster reduction in fossil fuel use will be needed to achieve the 1.5°C temperature goal.” That may be true (unless, for example, these or other developments render the 1.5°C

³³ The main reason for the extra scenarios in the 2023 Production Gap Report relative to in Green *et al.*’s analysis was the higher limit on BECCS (drawn from Fuss *et al.* 2018: 10.1088/1748-9326/aabf9f), which led to the inclusion of several additional scenarios from the REMIND model. In their original Supplementary Materials, Green *et al.* also cite [Hare *et al.* 2018](#) as the source of their method, which also used a threshold for BECCS of 5 Gt CO₂.

³⁴ I calculated this based on Green *et al.*’s own interpretation of UNEP’s [Production Gap Report 2023](#), as in their data S1 as was updated on July 31, 2025. Note also that in their [July 31, 2025 Erratum](#), Green *et al.* state that “The corrected pathway in the UNEP PGR median scenario still falls within the producing and underdevelopment fields”, but that is not strictly accurate: per data S1 (corrected), the PGR median is 2% *higher* than the sum of producing and under-development fields in 2035.

goal unattainable, or higher temperature overshoot is allowed) but it has little bearing over the accuracy of the scenario analysis in their original article, which is best judged using the information they had at available at the time.

Options for resolving Problem #3.

As I describe above, I have concerns with circular logic and bias in Green *et al.*'s methods for selecting scenarios. And yet, this problem is also subject to interpretation about which there could be reasonable disagreement. Nonetheless, to ensure a minimum standard of transparency in their evidence and conclusions, Green *et al.* should at least:

- a) Describe and justify what IPCC database variables they use for each of their three selection criteria (the variables they use are not currently listed);
- b) Describe how their scenario-selection choices affect their findings and perspectives on fossil fuel infrastructure, relative to alternate scenario sets (including, at least, the entire C1 scenario set) arising from alternate filtering methods.
- c) Not characterize their chosen scenarios as being "representative" or "credible", as that implies greater robustness than is warranted.

Beyond these solutions, I expect the authors may not be fully persuadable on my concerns. Still, I would urge the authors to consider two additional corrections that would increase robustness and transparency:

- d) Strengthen the logic on scenario filters for carbon sequestration. At present, the authors' feasibility criteria mix sources (Fuss *et al.* 2018 and IPCC AR6 WGIII Annex III) in ways that appear inconsistent. As an alternative, the authors should consider whether, for example, their thresholds can be based on a single, robust source, instead of mixing and matching between sources. Altering the set of selected scenarios may, of course, change Green *et al.*'s findings.
- e) Engage in a richer discussion of trade-offs between the scenarios selected by the authors and those that were discarded, especially with regards to feasibility and "the world we are in". At present, the authors scenario selection method essentially reduces to an argument about what is more feasible: behavioral and institutional break-throughs in the immediate term (Green *et al.*'s implicit view), or technology break-through on carbon sequestration within the next several years (in Green *et al.*'s discarded scenarios). Recognizing this, the authors could discuss the unique challenges displayed by their selected scenarios (e.g. faster retirement of existing coal-fired power plants, higher carbon prices, faster adoption of vegetarian diets), and how those challenges may interact with the authors' own political

considerations, e.g. the trade unions, public, or legislators already invoked by Green *et al.* in their political economy section (beginning on page 955, third column). Engaging in this richer discussion could make the analysis and conclusions more trustworthy.

Discussion and conclusions

In this document, I outlined three problems with a Policy Forum article published in *Science* magazine, one of the world's leading journals of peer-reviewed scientific research. *Science's* [Editorial Policies](#) emphasize quality and transparency when it comes to data, analytical methods, and research materials, as well as a commitment to [correcting errors](#) in published papers. I believe the Green *et al.* paper to have important errors, as detailed above, that deserve attention by the authors.

Green *et al.* present new, original research in their Policy Forum, and the authors (or their respective institutions) have promoted the article as meeting a high scientific standard. For example, IISD (an affiliation of authors Bois von Kursk and Muttitt) has promoted the article as the “first peer-reviewed article to show that there is no room for new fossil fuel projects under a 1.5°C global warming limit”³⁵ and author Muttitt has cited it as providing “strong scientific evidence that no new oil and gas fields should be opened if the world is to limit warming to 1.5°C”³⁶. Furthermore, the authors titled their February 2026 eLetter, “The scientific basis for a ‘no new fossil fuel projects’ norm is stronger than ever”. These quotes provide evidence that the authors aspire – like *Science* magazine itself -- to a high and trustworthy research standard.

The accuracy and robustness of Green *et al.* is important for practical matters, as well. Policy processes and legal claims may be relying on its findings.³⁷

In closing, the need to transition away from fossil fuels globally is well-established and crucial to limiting global warming to agreed-upon levels. But the energy transition also

³⁵ <https://www.iisd.org/publications/brief/no-new-fossil-fuel-projects-norm-we-need> (Accessed December 19, 2025).

³⁶ Muttitt, Greg (2025). Canadian Oil and Gas Production in the Global Clean Energy Transition: Outlook and economic risks. IISD and Environmental Defence. (Accessed December 19, 2025).

³⁷ For example, a [January 2026 article](#) “The State Duty Not to Approve New Fossil Fuels: Converging Science and Law” (accessed January 30, 2026) discusses the growing number of such court cases focused on new fossil fuel projects, while incorrectly claiming that “none of” Green *et al.*'s 26 scenarios include new fossil fuel developments. A [March 2026 article](#) “Science in the courtroom: evidentiary needs in climate litigation” cited Green *et al.*'s finding that “existing fossil fuel capital stock is sufficient to meet energy demands implied by representative 1.5°C scenarios” as a potential “red line” that companies must follow in the context of climate litigation.

requires trustworthy evidence if it is to keep its momentum. As I have shown here, Green *et al.* falls short. To meet *Science*'s standards for quality and transparency, Green *et al.*'s article should be corrected.

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Declaration of competing interests

Peter Erickson has advised and provided expert testimony for environmental organizations engaged in climate-related litigation against fossil fuel development.

Attachment 1. Default Energy Content for Liquids Used by Rystad Energy

Rystad Energy, a private consultancy, does not publish its data sources or methods for its UCube database. However, they did respond to an email requesting the default energy content for liquids, and which verifies UCube's default energy content for liquids as 1 barrel = 1 barrel oil *equivalent* = 6.12 GJ.³⁸

As described in the main text, using a single default energy content for all liquids globally may be understandable from the perspective of Rystad's primary audience, which is petroleum industry clients seeking to align business activities around some number of the 80,000 or more oil and gas fields in the database. (With so many fields, developing an accurate estimate of the energy content of any given field's liquids would be very difficult.)

However, the default energy content of 6.12 GJ/bbl becomes a problem when attempting to aggregate oil production *globally* across these fields for purposes of comparing to other sources, as in Green *et al.* Many of these liquids have considerably lower energy content, more like 4 GJ/bbl. Because of this, Rystad themselves do a conversion when they show their liquids data on the same chart as scenarios from other sources. Two examples from publicly available Rystad Energy reports are shown on the next page.³⁹

³⁸ Email communication with Debbie Lee of Rystad Energy, February 8, 2026 (full email exchange available upon request).

³⁹ The first chart is from Rystad Energy Energy 2024. Deep-dive on Energy Security. January 31, 2024. <https://www.og21.no/siteassets/dypdykk-2023-forsyningssikkerhet/20240131-rystad-energy---og21---dypdykkstudie-om-forsyningssikkerhet---final-report.pdf>. The second chart is from the following report (in Norwegian) which does the same thing but labels each of the scenarios: https://www.regjeringen.no/contentassets/f5fc522f50674c1f9e0b5db47c264dbe/netto-klimagassutslipp-fra-okt-olje-og-gassproduksjon-pa-norsk-sokkel_hovedrapport.pdf

Global liquids demand scenarios*

Million boe per day

* OPEC, IEA, EQNR, BP and Shell 2021 are adjusted to Rystad Energy's view on demand in 2021.
Source: Rystad Energy research and analysis; OPEC; IEA; Equinor; BP

Global væskeetterspørsel i ulike scenarier*

Millioner fat o.e./dag

*OPEC, IEA, EQNR, BP og Shell 2021 er justert slik at de er like Rystad Energys syn på etterspørsel historisk (2021). Trenden fremover er justert med samme faktor.
Kilde: Rystad Energy, OPEC, IEA, Equinor, BP

In their February 2026 eLetter, Green *et al.* discuss how energy contents from Rystad, IEA, Energy Institute, US EIA, OPEC, and others may differ, and how this is not necessarily a problem, “since oil production is usually measured by volume (barrels), and different types of oil have different energy density, modellers and data providers convert volumes to energy by different methods.” What Green *et al.* do not share, however, is that EIA’s energy content is not actually in the same units (EIA uses [gross calorific value](#) instead of the international standard of net calorific value for its energy units) and OPEC’s energy content is anomalously high (but for unknown reasons): see table below.⁴⁰ Green *et al.*’s energy content of 6.1 GJ/barrel is not appropriate for their purposes.

Institution	Global oil demand in 2022		Imputed energy content GJ/barrel	Notes on imputed energy content	Sources
	Energy (EJ)	Volume (mbpd)			
IEA	190	97	5.4		Energy: <i>World Energy Balances</i> Volume: <i>World Energy Outlook 2024</i>
Energy Institute	193	98	5.4	(Formerly BP)	<i>Statistical Review of World Energy</i>
US EIA	206	100	5.7	US EIA reports energy on GCV basis, when adjusted down by standard 5% to LCV is 5.4 GJ/barrel	US EIA International Energy data
OPEC	203	97	5.7	Known to be anomalously high. Other researchers adjust to 5.4 GJ/barrel	Energy: WOO 2023 Table 2.1. Volume: WOO 2023 Table 4.1 ⁴¹
Rystad Energy	220	98	6.1 ⁴²	Known to be anomalously high. Rystad themselves adjust others' values up to 1 boe/barrel (6.1 EJ/barrel) when comparing	Energy: Green <i>et al.</i> 's data S1 Volume: Rystad's <i>Upstream Trends Report</i> ⁴³
Notes					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All values here represent oil consumption (excluding biofuels) to align with the data presented in Green <i>et al.</i>'s eLetter. - IEA, Energy Institute, and Rystad Energy values were reported in EJ. EIA value converted using 1 QBTU = 1.055 EJ. OPEC value converted using 1 boe = 6.119 GJ. 					

⁴⁰ For a comprehensive attempt to convert EIA, OPEC, and other institutions’ oil demand values to common units, see [Raimi and Newell 2024](#), Global Energy Outlook Comparison Methods: 2024 Update

⁴¹ Energy units from Table 2.1 in *World Oil Outlook 2023*. Volumetric units from Table 4.1, after removing biofuels, GTLs, and CTLs to better align with data in Table 2.1.

⁴² Note this matches the energy content reported by Rystad Energy via email (see footnote earlier in this Attachment)

⁴³ Rystad provides such reports privately to UCube subscribers and which Green *et al.* must therefore have access to. (Sample Upstream Trends Report available upon request.)

Returning now to the original observation in Problem #1, which was that Green *et al.* list historical oil global extraction as being 220 EJ in 2022. As I have shown, that value is too high and using it without adjustment is inconsistent with the view of the data provider, Rystad Energy. As a final point of evidence, pasted below is a chart from Rystad’s *Global Energy Scenarios 2025*,⁴⁴ which shows global oil demand in 2022 being about 190 EJ, indistinguishable from IEA’s estimate.

Press Release

Fossil fuel demand by energy carrier

Exajoules (EJ)

A Rystad Energy Graphic
Source: Rystad Energy’s Energy Macro Solution, October 2025

⁴⁴ Accessed March 9, 2026 at <https://www.rystadenergy.com/news/global-energy-scenarios-2025-the-next-energy-era>.

Attachment 2. The 26 IPCC 1.5°C (C1) Scenarios analyzed by Green et al. 2024

The table below lists the 26 C1 scenarios listed in Green et al.’s table S2, along with their oil, gas, and global unabated gas power capacity values extracted from the IPCC AR6 database.

In their February 6, 2026 eLetter, Green et al. describe their method for assessing whether “new fossil fuel projects are needed” (original article, page 954, column 3) is to compare the median and interquartile values of demand to supply from existing infrastructure, and evaluate whether demand “is less than or approximately matches”. This allows them to judge whether ceasing new fossil investment would lead to a “significant threat of failing to meet energy demand” (or, alternately, “not create significant disruptions to 1.5°C-aligned energy demand.”)⁴⁵

Model	Scenario	IMP	Oil production (EJ)					Gas production (EJ)					Unabated gas power, GW					Significant (20%) disruption in supply of:	
			2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	Global energy	Regional gas power
			MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.0	LowEnergyDemand_1.3_IPCC	IMP-LD	187	99	99	47	129	-	68	-	33	-	-	-	-	-
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.1	EN_NPI2020_450		191	142	99	69	46	145	105	74	58	45	1,867	1,184	520	463	563		India+,SSA
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.1	EN_NPI2020_500		191	149	112	83	58	145	114	85	68	58	1,867	1,284	645	555	707		India+,SSA
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.1	EN_NPI2020_600_COV		185	163	138	111	86	134	118	115	99	93	1,633	1,652	1,612	1,050	947	Gas,	India+,SSA
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.1	EN_NPI2020_600_DR1p		184	157	128	102	79	135	114	88	76	75	1,668	1,251	575	477	671		India+,SSA
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.1	EN_NPI2020_600_DR2p		186	160	131	104	80	138	117	91	82	80	1,732	1,321	647	531	676		India+,SSA
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.1	EN_NPI2020_600_DR3p		188	163	133	106	82	142	120	96	82	83	1,783	1,401	796	564	742	Gas,	India+,SSA
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.1	EN_NPI2020_600_DR4p		189	166	135	106	81	143	123	100	85	86	1,832	1,500	921	629	761	Gas,	India+,SSA
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.1	NGFS2_Divergent Net Zero Policies		185	151	117	89	68	134	117	113	93	79	1,633	1,711	1,539	962	747		India+,SSA
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.1	NGFS2_Net-Zero 2050		185	159	134	106	81	134	111	105	92	91	1,633	1,371	1,165	849	866	Gas,	India+,SSA
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.2	COV_GreenPush_550		181	150	120	91	69	124	128	104	87	83	-	-	-	-	-	Gas,	
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.2	COV_NoPolicyNoCOVID_550		198	159	119	87	61	138	126	94	75	64	-	-	-	-	-		
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.2	COV_Restore_550		182	160	125	95	70	123	124	96	78	77	-	-	-	-	-		
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.2	COV_SelfReliance_550		178	161	123	93	68	126	131	101	81	77	-	-	-	-	-		
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.2	COV_SmartUse_550		179	154	120	92	68	125	132	102	83	82	-	-	-	-	-	Gas,	
REMIND 2.1	LeastTotalCost_LTC_brkLR15_SSP1_P50		193	193	196	193	176	128	133	135	116	89	1,964	2,365	2,718	2,447	2,043	Oil,Gas,Power	India+,SSA
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	CEMICS_SSP1-1p5C-minCDR		189	186	184	165	118	124	120	105	68	30	1,856	2,015	1,933	1,357	895	Oil,GasPower	India+,SSA
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	CEMICS_SSP2-1p5C-minCDR		193	191	173	149	125	129	122	89	47	15	1,967	1,992	1,465	770	429		India+,SSA
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	EN_NPI2020_600f_COV		176	176	184	185	170	122	123	123	108	93	1,727	1,883	2,114	2,006	1,919	Oil,Gas,Power	India+,SSA
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	SusDev_SDP-PkBudg1000	IMP-SP	186	182	177	165	146	130	129	127	103	80	1,844	2,144	2,439	2,255	2,160	Oil,GasPower	India+,SSA
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.3	DeepElec_SSP2_HighRE_Budg900	IMP-Ren	196	203	190	154	104	133	113	89	69	55	1,853	1,762	1,584	1,424	1,289	Gas Power	India+,SSA
WITCH 5.0	EN_NPI2020_400f		187	173	157	142	126	137	108	83	76	77	1,294	1,066	853	685	556		SSA
WITCH 5.0	EN_NPI2020_450		187	151	101	72	53	137	106	78	63	60	1,294	1,146	913	727	579		
WITCH 5.0	EN_NPI2020_450f		187	175	161	148	135	137	108	85	79	80	1,294	1,065	853	687	558	Oil,	SSA
WITCH 5.0	EN_NPI2020_500		187	161	129	97	75	137	106	80	65	64	1,294	1,114	896	716	572		
WITCH 5.0	EN_NPI2020_500f		187	179	165	154	143	137	109	87	82	83	1,294	1,069	858	692	563	Oil,Gas,	SSA
	Median		187	161	132	106	80	134	118	95	80	78	1,633	1,268	856	686	625	Count: 13	Count: 18
	Existing Infrastructure (Green et al.)		207	221	190	149	121	137	140	116	90	68	1,764	1,853	1,551	1,176	922		

Here I attempt to replicate Green et al.’s findings, by defining a “significant disruption” as one for which demand does not exceed supply from existing infrastructure by more than 20% in 2030, 2035, or 2040. (I also adjust existing oil infrastructure to match the IPCC median in 2020, to approximate the authors’ method in the Supplementary Materials to their eLetter.⁴⁶)

⁴⁵ The standard for comparison is further muddled in Figure SM.1 of their eLetter, which shows a 65th percentile that appears to approximately match supply in the mid-2030s, but which authors describe as being “well within forecasted oil supply until 2040”.

⁴⁶ My method is not *identical*, as the eLetter Supplementary Materials does not provide the authors’ own, custom adjusted 2020 value: their results are instead *indexed* to 2020=100 (note: the y-axis in Fig SM.1 is incorrectly labeled EJ/year). My adjustment reduces oil supply from existing fields by 10% in all years.

As shown in the last set of columns in the table, six scenarios for oil, nine scenarios for gas, five scenarios for global gas power, and 13 scenarios across these three variables display demand levels such that, without new fossil fuel infrastructure, “significant disruptions” to global energy supply would occur. These 13 scenarios are also marked with **bold** text in the table above, and they are shown super-imposed on Green *et al.*’s figure on the next page. These 13 scenarios constitute half of Green *et al.*’s scenarios; they alone disprove the claim that a “majority” of the authors’ 26 scenarios would not need new fossil fuel infrastructure.

Furthermore, considering that 18 scenarios would experience significant regional disruptions in unabated gas power in sub-Saharan Africa and south Asia (see also charts on last page of this attachment), the total number of Green *et al.*’s scenarios needing new fossil fuel infrastructure to avoid “significant disruptions” is 20 (77% of their set of 26). (The authors’ observation that cost pressures and stranded-asset risks push against the case for new unabated gas power in these regions is interesting but is not sufficient justification to selectively override specific findings of the IPCC scenarios; furthermore, some of those economics are already included in the scenarios, as the fraction – but not necessarily the importance – of total installed power capacity that is unabated gas drops steadily over time from a starting point of about 20% in Africa and 10% in South Asia.)

One interesting outcome of this exercise is that two of the IPCC’s “Illustrative Mitigation Pathways” (IMPs) would, without new fossil fuel infrastructure, experience significant disruptions in supply. These are tagged IMP-SP and IMP-REN in the third column above, and Green *et al.* actually did evaluate these two scenarios individually in their Supplementary Materials, where they used them (in part) to claim “further evidence supporting the conclusion that no new fossil fuel infrastructure is necessary to meet demand.” And yet, as shown in the table above, IMP-SP allows for new oil fields *and* new gas power (and also new gas fields, if the arbitrary 20% threshold for “significant disruption” were relaxed); IMP-REN allows for new unabated gas power in southern Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa.

The IMP-SP scenario (SP is for “Shifting Pathways”) is especially interesting, because it is meant to illustrate “how shifting global pathways towards sustainable development, including by reducing inequality, can lead to mitigation”.⁴⁷ It is just one scenario, but its findings (as well as the fact that the IPCC chose to highlight it as one of just three IMPS for the C1 scenario set) indicate that equitable sustainable development considerations (beyond climate change) may imply a view on the “need” or “room” for new fossil fuel

⁴⁷ IPCC AR6 WGIII, Chapter 3, page 309. This scenario is also referred to as IMP-SD. Interestingly, in their Supplementary Materials,

infrastructure that is less definitive than Green *et al.*'s conclusions. Indeed, it is difficult to imagine that room could not be made for poor regions of the world to develop a select number of new, peaking gas power plants (for example).

Lastly, even the methods for assessing “needs” for new fossil fuel infrastructure above may be conservative. An alternative way to assess whether each scenario “needs” new oil and gas using Green *et al.*'s data could be to calculate, for each scenario, its post-peak decline rate in oil and gas demand, and then compare those values to the decline-rates for existing oil and gas fields (respectively), as calculated from Green *et al.*'s Rystad data. This method could be preferred in part because, as Green *et al.* note in their eLetter, the IPCC scenarios assume slightly different base year oil and gas demand. Doing such a calculation,⁴⁸ I find that 24 of the scenarios in the table above would leave room for new oil, gas, or gas power.

⁴⁸ More specifically, I calculated the year of peak oil and gas demand (between 2020 and 2040 inclusive) for each scenario. If the peak was after 2020, I assumed the scenario would need new fields, since oil supply would need to increase in the near term. If the peak was *in* 2020 (as it was for most fields), I calculated a simplistic exponential decline rate between the peak year and 2040, and compared that to the annual decline rates from already-producing oil and gas fields from Green *et al.*'s data S1 of 4.1% and 5.6%, respectively.

Green et al.'s figure, annotated with their 13 (of 26) scenarios that would see significant disruptions in global supply without new fossil fuel infrastructure

1 Gas extraction

2 Oil extraction

- New exploration
- New field
- Field under development
- Producing fields
- Selected IPCC 1.5°C pathways including interquartile range
- IEA NZE 2023

3 Unabated coal power generation capacity

4 Unabated gas power generation capacity

- Announced
- Pre-permit
- Permitted
- In construction
- Operating
- Selected IPCC 1.5°C pathways including interquartile range
- IEA NZE 2023

IEA, International Energy Agency; IPCC, Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change; NZE, Net Zero Emissions.

The charts below show unabated gas power capacity in Green *et al.*'s scenarios (extracted from version 1.1 of the IPCC AR6 scenario database) for countries of South Asia and sub-Saharan Africa. The grey areas show capacity of operating and under-construction units in these regions extracted from the Global Oil and Gas Plant Tracker (January 2026 release).⁴⁹ Since starting values for these regions vary, I also show results indexed to 2025.⁵⁰

⁴⁹ Green *et al.* used a 2023 version of the database that I did not have access to. Instead, I applied the method documented in Green *et al.*'s Supplementary Materials to the 2026 version, assigning start and end dates to plants fueled entirely or partially with gas. I extracted plants in India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Sri Lanka, which ended up closely matching the IPCC median capacity for South Asia in 2020. For sub-Saharan Africa, I extracted plants in that "sub-region" (column AI) of the database.

⁵⁰ I indexed to 2025 here (not 2020), since the capacity of operating and under-construction plants peaked in this year in the 2026 version of the Global Oil and Gas Plant Tracker (I did not have the 2023 version).

Attachment 3. Feasibility Assessment of Scenario Sets

As described in Green *et al.*'s Supplementary Text, the IPCC rates its scenarios on 18 feasibility indicators (in Chapter 3 of IPCC AR6 WGIII). For each of the 18 indicators, the IPCC selects relevant thresholds to define three levels of concern: *high*, *medium*, and *low*. (See IPCC AR6 WGIII Anex III). Green *et al.* exclude C1 scenarios that meet the *medium* level of concern (or higher) in three indicators: fossil CCS, BECCS and afforestation/ reforestation.⁵¹

The IPCC uses several different methods for aggregating these feasibility concerns across dimensions and across time. Several of the aggregation methods use geometric means, and for which feasibility concerns were assigned a rating of 3 for high, 2 for medium, and 1 for low, based on their performance against each of the 18 indicators.

The chart below shows one such aggregation of feasibility concerns across all dimensions, following the method used in Figure 3.43 (panel B) of Chapter 3 of IPCC AR6 WGIII.⁵² As shown, Green *et al.*'s selected C1 scenarios show greater overall feasibility concern in the near term (through 2030), compared to those C1 scenarios discarded by the authors. By 2040, feasibility concerns are similar. In later decades, Green *et al.*'s scenarios show fewer feasibility concerns.

⁵¹ As discussed in their Supplemental Text, Green *et al.* do not use the IPCC's threshold for forest cover (which was intended to assess feasibility of afforestation, per the underlying source Brutschin *et al.* 2021: doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abf0ce), but instead substitute their own threshold for afforestation and reforestation.

⁵² To do this, I used the IPCC feasibility data published alongside Achakulwisut *et al.* 2023. Specifically, I used data in the field "concern_overall" in the following file: https://github.com/ploy-a/NCOMMS-AR6-FF/blob/main/data_raw/data_feasibility_indicators_18_06_2022.csv

Figure 3. Composite feasibility score (obtained by geometric mean of underlying indicators) over time for Green et al.'s scenarios compared to the C1 scenarios they discarded. Note that, due to data availability, this chart includes feasibility data from 24 of 26 of Green et al.'s scenarios, and 61 of 71 of the scenarios they discarded.

One way to think about this is that Green *et al.*'s scenarios follow a more disruptive transformation in the near term, which then leads to reduced long-term challenges in later decades.⁵³

More specifically, Green *et al.*'s scenario set shows higher levels of concern in four of the five over-arching feasibility dimensions evaluated by the IPCC. Namely, Green *et al.*'s set of 26 scenarios shows higher feasibility concern than the discarded scenarios in 2030 in:⁵⁴

- The **economic dimension** (composite score in 2030 of 2.2 vs 2.1), with Green *et al.*'s set displaying higher feasibility concerns due to needed carbon prices and rates of coal-plant retirements. Furthermore, all 24 of Green *et al.*'s scenarios assessed on the carbon price and coal-plant retirement criteria exceeded the authors' own threshold of a medium level of concern (rating of 2 or higher).
- The **technological dimension** (composite score 1.3 vs 1.2), owing especially to high concern over the feasibility of solar and wind power to scale at such rapid rates; All but one of Green *et al.*'s 23 scenarios assessed on solar and wind scale-up received a *medium* or *high* concern rating.⁵⁵

⁵³ As mentioned in the main text, Green *et al.*'s 26 scenarios exceed their own threshold ("medium" level of concern, or a rating of 2) in at least 6 (and some exceed in as many as 11) of 15 other criteria, and which helps explain why the composite feasibility rating approaches 2 in 2030 in the chart.

⁵⁴ By 2050, Green *et al.*'s scenarios have lower concern in the technological and economic dimensions.

⁵⁵ The one scenario that did not receive a medium or high rating for solar and wind scale-up was SusDev_SDP-PkBudg1000 also known the Illustrative Mitigation Pathway IMP-SP.

- The **socio-cultural dimension** (composite score 1.5 vs 1.2), owing especially to greater decrease in pasture cover, decrease in livestock meat consumption,⁵⁶ and increase in forest cover;⁵⁷ and
- The **institutional dimension** (composite score 2.8 vs 2.6), owing to unprecedented governance challenges and pace of per-capita CO₂ emission reductions.

In the fifth dimension, **geophysical concerns**, Green *et al.*'s scenarios display equivalent feasibility concerns in 2030 (1.0 in both subsets), but which grow to be 1.1 (in Green *et al.*'s set) versus 1.3 (in the discarded scenarios) by mid-century, owing mainly to lower concerns over biomass energy production in Green *et al.*'s set.

By selecting their 26 scenarios as they did, Green *et al.* are implicitly arguing that their preferred concerns over BECCS, fossil CCS, and afforestation / reforestation pose substantially greater feasibility challenges than do the combined concerns (across all criteria) above. That argument contrasts, at least in the near term, with the IPCC's own assessment in Chapter 3 of IPCC AR6 WGIII. Green *et al.*'s findings are fragile.

⁵⁶ The MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM_1.1 model, from which all nine of its C1 scenarios are in Green *et al.*'s set, appears to feature dietary changes (reduced meat consumption) to an extent that it raises socio-cultural feasibility concerns for rural land use and livelihoods (decrease in pasture cover) and the pace of change away from meat consumption in people's diets.

⁵⁷ The WITCH 5.0 model's five C1 scenarios, all of which are in Green *et al.*'s set, receive ratings of "high" concern for feasibility of forest cover increase (which is afforestation). This is interesting because it shows that high concerns can exist even for scenarios did not exceed the authors' threshold for afforestation and reforestation of 3.6 Gt CO₂/yr by 2050. That, in turn, raises the question of the extent to which a pass/fail feasibility filter for this variable is an appropriately useful method by which to analyze the scenarios.

Scenarios that display low concern for wind power

Under Problem #2, I described a counterfactual example in which researchers concerned about the feasibility of scaling wind power used the same “medium” threshold used by Green *et al.* to choose their scenarios. Below, those scenarios that show low feasibility concern for wind power (variable name: concern_wind) are flagged with a “1” in the last column; none of these are in Green *et al.*'s set of 26.

Model	Scenario	Oil production (EJ)					In Green <i>et al.</i>	Wind concern = low
		2020	2025	2030	2035	2040		
AIM/CGE 2.1	CD-LINKS_NP2020_400	205	203	183	152	134		
AIM/CGE 2.2	EN_NP2020_300f	201	176	148	135	151		
AIM/CGE 2.2	EN_NP2020_600	201	176	148	128	128		
AIM/Hub-Global 2.0	1.5C	197	194	176	137	103		
C-ROADS-5.005	Ratchet-1.5-limCDR-noOS							
C-ROADS-5.005	Ratchet-1.5-noCDR							
C-ROADS-5.005	Ratchet-1.5-noCDR-noOS							
COFFEE 1.1	EN_NP2020_400	180	150	147	141	123		
GCAM 4.2	SSP1-19	182		178		177		
GCAM 5.3	R_MAC_30_n0	193	193	148	162	160		1
GCAM 5.3	R_MAC_35_n8	193	196	178	121	157		1
GCAM 5.3	R_MAC_40_n8	193	197	198	175	131		1
GCAM 5.3	R_MAC_45_n8	193	199	202	194	172		1
GCAM 5.3	R_MAC_50_n8	193	200	204	203	189		1
GEM-E3_V2021	EN_NP2020_500	168	157	141	92	45		
GEM-E3_V2021	EN_NP2020_600_COV	154	153	149	129	94		
IMAGE 3.2	SSP1_SPA1_19I_D_LB	173	181	154	126	102		
IMAGE 3.2	SSP1_SPA1_19I_LIRE_LB	172	181	152	121	91		
IMAGE 3.2	SSP1_SPA1_19I_RE_LB	173	181	154	125	99		
IMAGE 3.2	SSP2_SPA1_19I_D_LB	173	187	167	142	117		1
IMAGE 3.2	SSP2_SPA1_19I_LIRE_LB	172	180	150	119	89		1
IMAGE 3.2	SSP2_SPA1_19I_RE_LB	173	188	165	138	110		1
IMAGE 3.2	SSP2_SPA2_19I_LI	172	182	180	168	128		
MESSAGE-GLOBIOM 1.0	ADVANCE_2020_1.5C-2100	202		136		67		
MESSAGE-GLOBIOM 1.0	EMF33_1.5C_cost100	216		126		61		
MESSAGE-GLOBIOM 1.0	EMF33_1.5C_full	218		125		62		
MESSAGE-GLOBIOM 1.0	SSP2-19	208		168		100		
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.0	CD-LINKS_NP2020_400	204		161		95		1
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.0	LowEnergyDemand_1.3_IPCC	187		99		47		1
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.1	EN_NP2020_450	191	142	99	69	46		1
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.1	EN_NP2020_500	191	149	112	83	58		1
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.1	EN_NP2020_600_COV	185	163	138	111	86		1
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.1	EN_NP2020_600_DR1p	184	157	128	102	79		1
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.1	EN_NP2020_600_DR2p	186	160	131	104	80		1
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.1	EN_NP2020_600_DR3p	188	163	133	106	82		1
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.1	EN_NP2020_600_DR4p	189	166	135	106	81		1
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.1	NGFS2_Divergent Net Zero Policies	185	151	117	89	68		1
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.1	NGFS2_Net-Zero 2050	185	159	134	106	81		1
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.2	COV_GreenPush_550	181	150	120	91	69		1
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.2	COV_NetPolicyNoCOVID_550	188	159	119	87	61		1
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.2	COV_Restore_550	182	160	125	95	70		1
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.2	COV_SelfReliance_550	178	161	123	93	68		1
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.2	COV_SmartUse_550	179	154	120	92	68		1
POLES ADVANCE	ADVANCE_2020_1.5C-2100	194	186	168	134	98		
POLES EMF33	EMF33_WB2C_cost100	204		169		143		
POLES EMF33	EMF33_WB2C_full	204		171		146		
POLES EMF33	EMF33_WB2C_nofuel	204		170		143		
REMIND 1.7	ADVANCE_2020_1.5C-2100	201	205	204	198	185		1
REMIND 1.7	CEMICS-1.5-CDR12	188	185	174	157	128		
REMIND 1.7	CEMICS-1.5-CDR20	188	196	204	200	187		1
REMIND 1.7	CEMICS-1.5-CDR8	188	150	123	86	56		
REMIND 1.7	CEMICS-2.0-CDR8	188	195	201	199	188		1
REMIND 2.1	CEMICS_GDPgrowth_1p5	193	197	198	190	169		
REMIND 2.1	CEMICS_HousingConst_1p5	193	199	201	190	165		
REMIND 2.1	CEMICS_Linear_1p5	193	197	200	192	170		
REMIND 2.1	CEMICS_opt_1p5	193	196	196	185	161		
REMIND 2.1	LeastTotalCost_LTC_br4LR15_SSP1_P50	193	193	196	193	176		1
REMIND 2.1	R2p1_SSP1-PkBudg900	185	183	180	164	128		
REMIND 2.1	R2p1_SSP2-PkBudg900	185	187	187	171	135		
REMIND 2.1	R2p1_SSP5-PkBudg900	185	191	204	199	160		
REMIND-MagPIE 1.5	SSP2-19	194		199		151		
REMIND-MagPIE 1.7-3.0	CD-LINKS_NP2020_400	197	202	204	198	185		1
REMIND-MagPIE 1.7-3.0	EMF33_1.5C_nofuel	195	194	195	197	191		1
REMIND-MagPIE 1.7-3.0	PEP_1p5C_full_eff	190	192	192	183	169		1
REMIND-MagPIE 1.7-3.0	PEP_1p5C_red_eff	190	179	157	135	113		
REMIND-MagPIE 1.7-3.0	PEP_2C_red_eff	190	192	191	185	173		1
REMIND-MagPIE 1.7-3.0	SMP_2C_lifesty	194	203	210	213	211		1
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	CEMICS_SSP1-1p5C-fullCDR	189	190	195	188	162		
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	CEMICS_SSP1-1p5C-minCDR	189	186	184	165	118		1
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	CEMICS_SSP2-1p5C-fullCDR	193	199	203	195	173		
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	CEMICS_SSP2-1p5C-minCDR	193	191	173	149	125		1
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	EN_NP2020_200f	186	189	192	180	150		
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	EN_NP2020_300f	186	189	193	184	155		
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	EN_NP2020_400	186	170	154	117	77		
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	EN_NP2020_400f	186	190	196	189	163		
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	EN_NP2020_500	186	183	176	152	110		
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	EN_NP2020_600	186	188	190	177	145		
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	EN_NP2020_600_COV	176	173	177	172	147		
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	EN_NP2020_600f_COV	176	176	184	185	170		1
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	NGFS2_Divergent Net Zero Policies	178	176	169	145	105		
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	NGFS2_Net-Zero 2050	178	181	181	166	132		
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	NGFS2_Net-Zero 2050_IP0_95th	178	180	178	162	129		
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	NGFS2_Net-Zero 2050_IP0_median	178	180	178	162	129		
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	SusDev_SDP-PkBudg1000	186	182	177	165	146		1
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	SusDev_SSP1-PkBudg900	186	184	183	167	131		
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.2	SusDev_SSP2-PkBudg900	186	189	191	176	139		
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.3	DeepElec_SSP2_HighRE_Budg900	196	203	190	154	104		1
REMIND-MagPIE 2.1-4.3	DeepElec_SSP2_def_Budg900	196	207	204	184	142		
WITCH 5.0	EN_NP2020_400f	187	173	157	142	126		1
WITCH 5.0	EN_NP2020_450	187	151	101	72	53		1
WITCH 5.0	EN_NP2020_450f	187	175	161	148	135		1
WITCH 5.0	EN_NP2020_500	187	161	129	97	75		1
WITCH 5.0	EN_NP2020_500f	187	179	165	154	143		1
WITCH-GLOBIOM 3.1	SSP1-19	194		95		75		
WITCH-GLOBIOM 3.1	SSP4-19	207		121		98		
WITCH-GLOBIOM 4.4	CD-LINKS_NP2020_1000	216	202	189	179	166		
WITCH-GLOBIOM 4.4	CD-LINKS_NP2020_400	216	190	140	107	83		
							26	17
	(1) Median of Green <i>et al.</i> 's 26 scenarios:	187	161	132	106	80		
	(2) Median of 17 scenarios with low concern for wind power:	193	195	195	189	172		
	Ratio of median of (2) to median of (1)	1.0	1.2	1.5	1.8	2.1		